

PREVENTING VENTILATOR ASSOCIATED PNEUMONIA: KNOWLEDGE AND COMPLIANCE OF CRITICAL CARE NURSES IN LAHORE'S TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS

Rimsha Javed^{*1}, Meerab Ashraf², Mahreen Kousar³, Pranika Davi⁴, Faiza Munir⁵,
Habib Ullah Riaz⁶

^{*1,2,3,4,5}Nursing Officer, Shalamar Institute of Health Sciences, Shalamar Hospital Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

⁶Nursing Officer, MSN Scholar, University of Health Sciences, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

¹rimshajaved364@gmail.com, ²meerabashraf111@gmail.com, ³ali.mahr353@gmail.com,
⁴paranika.davi@gmail.com, ⁵fmunir916@gmail.com, ⁶jabtrakhaijan786786@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Rimsha Javed

Abstract

Background: Ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) is one of the most common healthcare associated infections among critically ill patients, particularly those receiving mechanical ventilation. Nurses play a pivotal role in the prevention of VAP through evidence based practices. However, variations in their knowledge and compliance remain a challenge, especially in low and middle income settings.

Aim and Objective: This study aimed to assess the knowledge and compliance of critical care nurses regarding VAP prevention and to determine the association between knowledge and compliance in tertiary care hospitals in Lahore, Pakistan.

Methodology: A descriptive cross sectional study was conducted from February to May 2022 at Services Hospital and Mayo Hospital, Lahore. A total of 100 critical care nurses were recruited using convenience sampling. Data were collected through a structured, close ended questionnaire. Knowledge and compliance levels were categorized into good, average, and poor based on predefined scoring criteria. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20, and the Chi square test was applied to assess associations between knowledge and compliance.

Results: The majority of participants (67%) had average knowledge of VAP prevention, while 25% demonstrated poor knowledge and only 8% exhibited good knowledge. In contrast, 97% of nurses showed good compliance with preventive measures, and only 3% had poor compliance. The Chi square test revealed no statistically significant association between knowledge and compliance ($p = 0.062$).

Conclusion: The findings suggest that although most nurses demonstrated good compliance with preventive practices, their knowledge levels were largely average. The lack of association between knowledge and compliance indicates that compliance may be influenced more by institutional protocols than by individual knowledge. Continuous professional education, training, and reinforcement of evidence-based guidelines are essential to enhance both knowledge and sustained practice among ICU nurses.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most common and deadly types of hospital-acquired (nosocomial) pneumonia is ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) (Aysha, El-Din et al. 2016). It affects about 28% of patients on mechanical ventilation (Othman and Abdelazim 2017) and is linked to a markedly higher risk of morbidity and death (Aloush and Alsaireh 2018). VAP is defined as hospital-acquired pneumonia that appears in patients on mechanical ventilation over 48 hours after ventilation starts (Bankanie, Outwater et al. 2021). Clinically, purulent tracheobronchial secretions, fever, leukocytosis, and a new or progressive pulmonary infiltrate are its hallmarks (Shivananda and Yashoda 2021).

VAP continues to be the most common infection among patients admitted to intensive care units (ICUs) (Ali, Khan et al. 2016). Its presence raises mortality rates (Mogyoródi, Dunai et al. 2016), lengthens hospital stays (Zeb, Hasnain et al. 2018), and increased healthcare costs (Bagheri-Nesami, Amiri-Abchuyeh et al. 2015). The migration of microorganisms into the lower respiratory tract, frequently as a result of aspiration in critically ill patients, is the main cause of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) (Zeb, Hasnain et al. 2018). Inadequate nursing knowledge and poor adherence to evidence-based VAP prevention protocols are additional contributing factors (Kalyan, Bibi et al. 2020). To guarantee the highest standards of patient care, nursing practice should be based on a substantial body of scientific evidence (Dumbre 2019).

Nurses must possess both adequate knowledge and the ability to integrate evidence based preventive measures into clinical practice (Chithra and Raju 2017). In this regard, several guidelines and evidence based recommendations have been developed for the prevention and management of VAP (Aloush and Al-Rawajfa 2020). The Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations (JCAHO) introduced the Ventilator Care Bundle (VCB), comprising four essential measures: elevation of the head of the bed, daily sedation interruption and assessment of readiness to extubate, prophylaxis for peptic ulcer disease, and prophylaxis for deep vein

thrombosis. Improved compliance with these measures has been shown to reduce mortality, ICU length of stay, overall hospital days, and healthcare expenditures (Aziz, Kausar et al. 2020). Preventive strategies should be initiated at the time of intubation and maintained until extubation (Ali 2013).

Problem Statement

Nurses play a critical role in the prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia. Patients admitted to ICUs and undergoing mechanical ventilation are at high risk of developing VAP. The incidence of VAP in ICU settings is closely related to nurses' knowledge and their compliance with preventive measures. An increasing patient load in critical care areas negatively impacts cost of therapy, length of hospital stay, and overall patient outcomes.

Although several studies have examined nurses' theoretical knowledge of VAP prevention, fewer have evaluated the translation of this knowledge into clinical practice. Furthermore, in Pakistan, limited research has been conducted to assess both the knowledge and adherence of nurses to standard guidelines for VAP prevention.

Objective

The objective of this study is to assess the knowledge and compliance of critical care nurses regarding ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) prevention in tertiary care hospitals of Lahore.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Definition and Classification of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia

Ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) is defined as a nosocomial infection that develops in patients receiving mechanical ventilation for more than 48 hours after intubation (Ali 2013). According to Craven et al. (2018), VAP is characterized by a new or progressive pulmonary infiltrate, fever, altered white blood cell count, and purulent tracheobronchial secretions (Craven, Wojcik et al. 2018). VAP is generally categorized into two types: early onset VAP, which occurs within the first 5 days

of mechanical ventilation, and late onset VAP, which develops after 5 days or more of ventilation (Ali 2013).

2.2 Prevalence and Burden of VAP

The European Prevalence of Infection in Intensive Care (EPIC) study, the largest ICU prevalence study conducted to date, revealed that almost half of all ICU acquired infections in Europe were due to VAP. Other studies have similarly shown that VAP accounts for more than 50% of infections among mechanically ventilated patients, making it the second most common ICU acquired infection after urinary tract infections (Chevret, Hemmer et al. 1993). VAP contributes to increased morbidity, mortality, length of hospital stay, and healthcare costs, making it a significant challenge in critical care settings worldwide (Mogyoródi, Dunai et al. 2016, Zeb, Hasnain et al. 2018).

2.3 Knowledge and Compliance of Nurses in VAP Prevention

Several studies have assessed ICU nurses' knowledge and compliance regarding VAP prevention. A cross sectional study in Tanzania found varying levels of knowledge and compliance among ICU nurses in implementing VAP bundle strategies in a resource limited setting (Bankanie, Outwater et al. 2021). Similarly, a descriptive study conducted in tertiary care ICUs in India revealed that although most nurses had average to good knowledge, their clinical practices did not necessarily reflect this knowledge. The study found no significant association between nurses' knowledge and compliance with VAP prevention measures, highlighting the need for strategies to improve adherence (Kalyan, Bibi et al. 2020, Bankanie, Outwater et al. 2021).

In Jordan, Alkhazali, Bayraktar, and AlMugheed (2021) reported that while nurses possessed adequate theoretical knowledge of VAP prevention, their understanding of specific preventive measures was limited. Barriers to VAP prevention included lack of equipment, lapses in sterile technique, and insufficient time for infection control practices. The study emphasized the importance of removing these barriers and providing ongoing professional development to improve patient outcomes (Alkhazali, Bayraktar et al. 2021).

2.4 Gaps in Implementation and Barriers to Compliance

Some research has indicated that nurses often implement VAP prevention strategies without full awareness or responsibility, which can undermine their effectiveness (Oliveira, Zagalo et al. 2014, Mogyoródi, Dunai et al. 2016). Lack of education and training has been consistently cited as a key barrier to proper implementation of the VAP bundle. Educational interventions have shown positive impacts. For example, a two year study in a 20bed medical ICU demonstrated that structured educational programs and periodic reminders significantly increased compliance with VAP prevention strategies (Abad, Formalejo et al. 2021).

2.5 Evidence from Pakistan

In Pakistan, similar trends have been observed. A cross sectional study conducted in public and private tertiary care facilities in Peshawar highlighted the need for continuous educational programs for nurses to improve their understanding of VAP prevention and reduce its incidence (Al Shameri 2017, Zeb, Hasnain et al. 2018).

Another cross sectional study in hospitals across Islamabad and Rawalpindi found that most participants had adequate knowledge and considerable experience, although gaps between knowledge and practice persisted (Shah et al., 2017).

2.6 Association Between Knowledge and Practice

The literature presents mixed findings on the relationship between nurses' knowledge and their clinical practices regarding VAP prevention. While some studies indicate a positive correlation between higher knowledge levels and better practices, others show no significant association, suggesting that knowledge alone is insufficient to ensure compliance (Kalyan, Bibi et al. 2020, Bankanie, Outwater et al. 2021).

3. METHODOLOGY

To evaluate critical care nurses' compliance and knowledge of ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) prevention, a cross-sectional study design was used. The study took place at Services Hospital and Mayo Hospital, two tertiary care hospitals in Lahore, over the course of four months, from February to May

2022. Regardless of gender, the study population included registered nurses with 1 to 6 years of clinical experience who worked in critical care units. 100 participants were chosen using a convenience sampling technique, according to the Rao soft sample size calculator. A pre-made, closed-ended questionnaire that evaluated two key variables knowledge and compliance was used to gather data. Each right response received one point for the knowledge assessment, while wrong answers received zero; good knowledge was indicated by scores above 8, average knowledge by scores between 6 and 8, and poor knowledge by scores below 6. "Yes" answers received a score of one, while "no" answers received a score of zero for compliance. Good compliance was denoted by scores greater than six, while poor compliance was denoted by scores less than six. Version 20 of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data. The data was summarized using descriptive statistics, and the relationship between compliance and knowledge was examined using the chi square test. The administrations of both hospitals granted their

ethical approval and consent for the collection of data. Prior to data collection, all nurses provided written informed consent, and participation was entirely voluntary. By keeping the data anonymous and safely stored in a locked file, confidentiality was rigorously upheld.

Results

The majority of nurses were relatively young professionals, as evidenced by the participants' mean age of 29.3 ± 3.5 years. Just 11% of respondents were men, compared to 89% of respondents who were women. The Medical ICU employed the greatest percentage of participants (38%), followed by the Surgical ICU (21%), COVID ICU (13%), Neonatal ICU (16%), and Paediatric ICU (12%). Of the nurses, 42% had 1-2 years of clinical experience in critical care, 35% had 3-5 years, and 23% had 6 years or more in the intensive care unit. This distribution shows that the nursing staff in the chosen tertiary care hospitals is primarily young and has a moderate level of experience.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants (N = 100)

Characteristics	Items	n (%) / Mean \pm SD
Age	Age (years)	29.3 \pm 3.5
Gender	Male	11 (11)
	Female	89 (89)
Department	Medical ICU	38 (38)
	Surgical ICU	21 (21)
	Pediatric ICU	12 (12)
	Neonatal ICU	16 (16)
	COVID ICU	13 (13)
Experience in ICU (years)	1-2 years	42 (42)
	3-5 years	35 (35)
	\geq 6 years	23 (23)

Critical care nurses' answers to knowledge-based questions about preventing ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) are shown in Table 2/Figure 1. The findings show that knowledge levels in various domains vary significantly. Ninety-five percent of nurses correctly identified the fact that oral microorganisms can cause infection. They also

acknowledged the significance of cleaning the oral cavity (88%), the risk factor of mechanical ventilation duration (86%), and the effect of oral care solutions in preventing bacterial colonisation (82%). Similarly, 76% of respondents accurately stated that the best way to prevent VAP is to use a closed suctioning system.

Figure 1: Level of knowledge

Table 2: Level of knowledge

Nonetheless, significant gaps in knowledge were noted. Only 16% of respondents could name a ventilator care bundle component, and only 6% were aware of the preferred method for endotracheal intubation. Furthermore, little was known about the prevalence of pneumonia in intensive care unit patients (26%), the suggested modifications to

ventilator circuits (37%), and the elevation of the head of the bed (65%). These results underline the necessity of focused educational initiatives to improve ICU nurses' understanding of important VAP prevention topics.

Figure 2: Level of knowledge

The participants' general level of knowledge about preventing ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is depicted in Figure 2. Just 8% of nurses had good knowledge, 25% had poor knowledge, and the majority (67%) had average knowledge. These results indicate that while the majority of participants have a basic understanding of VAP prevention, there is still

a considerable knowledge gap, underscoring the necessity of focused educational interventions.

Level of compliance to preventive measures

Nurses' adherence to ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) prevention measures is shown in Table 3/figure 3. The findings show that

recommended practices are generally followed to a high degree.

Figure 3: Level of compliance to preventive measures

Table:3 Level of compliance to preventive measures

Almost all of the participants reported using sterile techniques during tracheal suctioning (99%), changing gloves between patients (97%), practicing hand hygiene before and after each oral care, and providing daily oral care to intubated patients (99%). Additionally, high compliance was observed with

regard to implementing daily sedation vacations (85%), peptic ulcer prophylaxis (89%), deep vein thrombosis prophylaxis (87%), and ventilator circuit changes (92%).

Figure 4: Level of knowledge

The participants' overall level of compliance is further depicted in Figure 4. Just 3% of nurses showed poor compliance with VAP preventive measures, compared to 97% who showed good compliance. These results imply that while general adherence to advised practices is praiseworthy, some

preventive measures specifically, head-of-bed elevation and chlorhexidine oral care need more attention through monitoring and training in order to attain consistent compliance.

Knowledge & Compliance Cross tabulation

Table 4: Association of knowledge and compliance (N=100)

Knowledge Level	Compliance		Total	P-Value
	Poor	Good		
Poor	1 (1%)	24 (24%)	25 (25%)	0.062
Average	3 (3%)	64 (64%)	67 (67%)	
Good	2 (2%)	6 (6%)	8 (8%)	
Total	6 (6%)	94 (94%)	100 (100%)	

Table 4 shows the relationship between compliance and knowledge about preventing ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP). Of the 100 participants, the majority with average knowledge (64%) showed good compliance with preventive measures, and the majority with poor knowledge (24%) also followed recommended practices. It's interesting to note that only 6% of nurses with good knowledge demonstrated good compliance, while 2% demonstrated poor compliance. Regardless of their level of expertise, 94% of nurses showed good compliance overall. The correlation between knowledge and compliance, however, was not statistically significant, according to the Chi-square test ($p = 0.062$).

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the knowledge and compliance of intensive care unit (ICU) nurses employed at tertiary care hospitals in Lahore with regard to the prevention of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP). The results showed that while most nurses showed good compliance with suggested preventive measures, most had only average knowledge of VAP prevention. Remarkably, there was no statistically significant correlation between compliance and knowledge.

Consistent with earlier research, there is no correlation between compliance and knowledge. Kalyan et al. (2021) and Bankanie et al. (2021), for example, both noted that while ICU nurses adhered to VAP prevention protocols, they frequently did so without fully comprehending the guidelines, which reduced the practices' efficacy. This implies that institutional procedures and standard practices, rather than personal knowledge levels, may be more

strongly associated with compliance (Kalyan, Bibi et al. 2020, Bankanie, Outwater et al. 2021).

Other research, on the other hand, has shown a strong correlation between knowledge and compliance and revealed that ICU nurses' practices were directly impacted by their lack of knowledge. Insufficient comprehension of VAP bundles impeded effective prevention, according to Zeb et al. (2018), Aziz et al. (2020), and Mogyoródi et al. (2016). They emphasized that knowledge is a critical factor in determining evidence-based practice. These disparate findings might be the result of regional variations in resource availability, nurse-to-patient ratios, and healthcare environments (Aziz, Kausar et al. 2020)(Mogyoródi, Dunai et al. 2016, Zeb, Hasnain et al. 2018).

It is important to recognize the limitations of the current study. First off, the cross-sectional design makes it more difficult to determine a causal or temporal link between compliance and knowledge. Second, the results' ability to be applied outside of the study population is restricted by the convenience sampling method. Furthermore, a small percentage of nurses chose not to participate, which could have resulted in selection bias. Despite these drawbacks, the study's main strength is that it contributes to the scant body of research from Pakistan, where very few studies have looked at critical care nurses' practices and knowledge of VAP prevention.

Further investigation is required to examine additional potential determinants of VAP occurrence in ICU patients, such as workload, staffing ratios, resource availability, and adherence monitoring, as this study did not find a significant correlation between knowledge and compliance. To increase generalizability, larger and more varied samples

should be used in future research. To further improve nurses' knowledge and strengthen their adherence to evidence-based practices, hospitals should fund ongoing education and training initiatives. These programs are crucial for maintaining high standards of patient care and lowering the prevalence of ventilator-associated pneumonia.

Conclusion

This study evaluated critical care nurses' compliance and understanding of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) prevention in Lahore's tertiary care hospitals. The results showed that although most nurses showed good adherence to preventive measures, their general level of knowledge remained average. Significantly, there was no correlation between knowledge and compliance, indicating that routine practices and institutional protocols may have a greater influence on adherence to preventive measures than personal comprehension. These results emphasize how important it is to close the gap between theory and practice in order to maximize infection prevention in intensive care units.

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